

AARNIKOIVU, M., FILIPPOU, K., SUNDUKOVA, M., & ORAHOVAC, A.
(2023). RESEARCHER MENTAL HEALTH OVERVIEW IN FINLAND.
ZENODO. [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.10964556](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964556)

Researcher Mental Health Overview in Finland

DATE OF UPDATE:
November 23rd, 2022.

WRITTEN BY:
Melina Aarnikoivu
(MC for Finland)

Kalypso Filippou
(University of Turku)

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WHAT IS IN THE NEWS?

The following pieces of news are related to universities and are gathered from the past two years and are mostly from one of the biggest Finnish news sites, Yle - the state-owned national broadcasting company.

01

In 2018, there was a university merger of two institutions in Tampere, which led to the creation of "Tampere University" (formerly the University of Tampere and Tampere University of Technology). At the time, there was a great deal of resistance towards the new Regulations ("johtosääntö") and the staff was demonstrating and striking [1, 2]. In 2021, dozens of people were laid off, some resigned themselves, and many people faced drastic changes in their work tasks [3]. Some spaces were planned to be closed, reducing the physical working space of the staff [4]. These actions continue to cause dissatisfaction within the Tampere University community. There is a doctoral thesis that has recently been completed on the topic of the merger [5].

02

At the University of Helsinki, especially the humanities and arts have been targeted by funding cuts, causing a crisis especially in the musicology department but also elsewhere [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11].

03

In 2021, it became apparent that the pandemic had a significant negative effect on researchers and teachers. The quick - although somewhat smooth - transitioning to online teaching was hard for both teachers and students [12].

[1] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-10105283>

[2] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-10064861>

[3] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12208252>

[4] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12185444>

[5] <https://trepo.tuni.fi/handle/10024/141400>

[6] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-11857988>

[7] <https://areena.yle.fi/podcastit/1-50731661>

[8] <https://www.suoni.fi/etusivu/2021/3/24/kuulumisia>

[9] <https://www.hs.fi/mielipide/art-200007849654.html>

[10] <https://www.hs.fi/paivanlehti/09022021/art-2000007790743.html>

[11] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12234517>

[12] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12034611>

04

In 2021, the University of Eastern Finland announced that it would give a part-time employment contract to researchers who have external funding from elsewhere. This means that those researchers will be entitled to healthcare services they wouldn't otherwise have as grant researchers [13].

05

In social media, there have been several attacks on researchers where people - typically the ones outside of academia - criticise the topics and researchers that have been funded by different foundations or the Academy of Finland. These attacks have been condemned by universities [14, 15, 16]. It is possible that because of such attacks, many researchers in Finland do not want to publicly discuss their work or share their results.

06

In spring 2021, the government announced that the funding for the Academy of Finland - the biggest Finnish funding body for research - will have a smaller budget from 2023 onwards. This was heavily criticised by Finnish universities and the Academy of Finland itself [17, 18, 19]. However, the budget cut was later cancelled.

07

In November 2022, the University of Turku announced they will be implementing a "budget balancing programme" ("talouden tasapainottamisohjelma") between 2023-28, which might include layoffs [20].

08

In November 2022, a report commissioned by the Ministry of Education and Culture showed that Finnish higher education institutions still have much work to do in promoting equality for teaching and research staff [21]. (See more in the Equity and Diversity Section).

Mental health is regularly discussed in the Finnish media. Here are some latest pieces from the past couple of months:

- Only a third of those seeking help for mental health issues are men [22].
- Mieli ry (an association for mental health) organises regular "mental health emergency" training sessions [23].
- A study hypothesises that there could be 1 million fewer sick leave days per year if the mental health issues of workers were treated differently [24].
- Especially girls' and women's ADHD is still widely underdiagnosed [25].
- The war in Ukraine drastically increased calls to different mental health helplines [26].
- There is a dire need for more psychotherapists in Finland [27].

[13] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-11772971>

[14] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12087357>

[15] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12086106>

[16] <https://www.helsinki.fi/fi/uutiset/matematiikka-ja-luonnontieteet/tutkimuksen-hyotya-vaikea-ennakoida-siksi-tutkijoiden-pitaisi-saada-tutkia-juuri-sita-mita-he-haluavat>

[17] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-11950129>

[18] <https://www.aka.fi/suomen-akatemian-toiminta/ajankohtaista/tiedotteet-ja-uutiset/2021/vmn-budjettiesitys-40-miljoonan-uron-leikkaus-tutkimusrahoitukseen/>

[19] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12070894>

[20] <https://yle.fi/a/74-20004212>

[21] https://okm.fi/-/selvitys-korkeakoulujen-kiinnitettava-huomiota-etnisiin-vahemmistoihin-kuuluvan-henkiloston-tasa-arvoon?languageId=en_US (in English) and

https://okm.fi/-/selvitys-korkeakoulujen-kiinnitettava-huomiota-etnisiin-vahemmistoihin-kuuluvan-henkiloston-tasa-arvoon?languageId=fi_FI (in Finnish)

[22] <https://yle.fi/a/74-20003888>

[23] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/74-20003088>

[24] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/74-20003075>

[25] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12601127>

[26] <https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12350313>

[27] <https://www.hs.fi/kaupunki/helsinki/art-2000009074872.html>

In Finnish politics, mental health receives some attention. For example:

- In 2022, The government announced that the legislation on mental health and substance use will be updated [28].
- In June 2022, the parliament discussed young people's increased mental health issues, which showed that members of the parliament/ministers have widely varying views on the topic [29].
- In spring 2022, it seemed that the parliament was not going to include the so-called "therapy guarantee" in its programme [30].
- In spring 2023, there will be the next parliamentary election in Finland. Mielenterveyspooli ("Mental health pool") has set 10 goals for the next parliament regarding mental health. All the goals are listed in Finnish here: <https://mielenterveyspooli.fi/mielenterveyspoolin-eduskuntavaaliohjelman/>

[28]<https://valtioneuvosto.fi/-/1271139/mielenterveys-ja-paihdelainsaadantoa-uudistetaan>

[29]<https://www.is.fi/politiikka/art-2000008861022.html>

[30]<https://yle.fi/uutiset/3-12330734>

FUNDING FOR RESEARCH AND ACADEMIA

According to the latest statistics published by the State of Scientific Research in Finland review, Finland's R&D expenditure was 2.9 percent of GDP (R&D intensity) in 2020. By 2030, the Finnish Government aims to increase the share to 4 per cent [31]. "The state of research is constantly being monitored and reported in various statistics [32].

In 2019, the government approved a new funding model for Finnish higher education institutions. The funding model concerns the years 2021-24 [33]. The emphasis of the funding is on the number of completed degrees [34]. According to research, the Finnish funding model is one of the most "results-oriented" ones in the world [35], creating a great deal of pressure on researchers.

For several years, Finnish higher education and Finnish research have been under budget-cut threats. Even though the funding for research was reported to be safeguarded for 2022 [36], the future remains uncertain.

[31] <https://www.aka.fi/en/about-us/whats-new/press-releases/2022/state-of-scientific-research-finland-must-invest-in-research-and-development/>

[32] <https://www.aka.fi/suomen-akatemian-toiminta/ajankohtaista/blogi/2021/tieteen-tila-tilastot-tutkimusrahoitus/>

[33] <https://okm.fi/-/korkeakouluille-uusi-rahoitusmalli>

[34] <https://www.helsinki.fi/fi/uutiset/korkeakoulupolitiikka/yliopistojen-uusi-rahoitusmalli-korostaa-suoritettuja-tutkintoja>

[35] <https://politiikasta.fi/yliopistojen-rahoitusmalli-tuloksellisuusohjaus-ja-akateeminen-vastarinta/>

[36] <https://okm.fi/-/ministeri-kurvinen-tieteen-rahoitus-turvattiin-vuodelle-2022-tulevaisuuden-rahoitus-edellyttaa-priorisointia>

PERSONA OF THE RESEARCHER ON THE CAREER LADDER IN THE COUNTRY

Generally, Finland - like other Nordic countries - is known to be somewhat equal when it comes to education. Due to the lack of tuition fees and the existence of a student allowance system, higher education is, in theory, accessible to anyone (for criticism, see 37, 38, 39). However, studies have shown that one's educational level is still very much tied to the level of one's parents' education [40], and doctoral education is not an exception [41]. In a study by Nori and colleagues [42], it was found that there are three distinct groups to be identified among doctoral researchers in Finland: Status Raisers, Educational Inheritors, and Long-term Plodders. All these groups have different kinds of resources as well as chances to "survive" in academia. Especially the ones coming from less educated families who experience "imposter syndrome". Then again, the researchers suggested that the influence of family background might diminish as the person gets older.

There are now three times as many doctoral researchers studying in Finnish universities as there were 20 years ago, making the total number about 18,000 [43]. About 10,000 are women, and 8,000 are men.

AGE GROUP	NUMBER OF DOCTORAL RESEARCHERS (IN 2022)
20-24	87
25-29	3.204
30-34	4.431
35-39	3.486
40-44	2.517

[37] <https://suomenkuvalehti.fi/kotimaa/opintotuki-heikkenee-nuorten-asema-jo-valmiiksi-huono-syrjityminen-lisaantynyt/>
 [38] <https://vasemmisto.fi/nomineeposts/opiskelijoiden-opintoraha-liian-pieni-opintolainalla-opiskelu-ei-ole-kenellekaan-vaihtoehdo/>
 [39] <https://www.raahenseutu.fi/opintotuki-pakottaa-opintolainaan-jolloin-velkavan/3500855>
 [40] <https://www.tilastokeskus.fi/tietotrendit/artikkelit/2016/vanhempien-koulutus-vaikuttaa-lasten-valintoihin/>
 [41] https://www.stat.fi/artikkelit/2009/art_2009-03-16_002.html?s=0
 [42] <https://www.informingscience.org/Publications/4637?Source=%2FJournals%2FJIDS%2FArticles%3FVolume%3D0-0>
 [43] All the following numbers are gathered from Vipunen: https://vipunen.fi/en-gb/_layouts/15/xviewer.aspx?id=/en-gb/Reports/Yliopistokoulutuksen%20opiskelijat-n%C3%A4k%C3%B6kuulma-koulutusaste_EN.xlsx

45-49	1.797
50-54	1.134
55-59	894
60-64	555
65 or older	508

As can be seen from the table, most doctoral researchers are between the ages of 25 and 44 - only a handful begin their doctoral studies before that. This is because secondary education typically lasts until a person is 18 or 19, after which those pursuing a higher education degree in a university study first three years for a bachelor's degree and then two years for a master's degree. In reality, for many, it takes longer than five years to complete these two degrees [44, 45]. Many men also go to the army before attending higher education, delaying their HE studies by 1 year. All these factors contribute to the PhD also being pursued later. Additionally, due to the fact that in the past there were no time limits set for PhD completion, many pursued a PhD as a long-term project, rather than as something to be done in a few years. Moreover, doing a PhD part-time is not uncommon. Finally, some decide to pursue a PhD only after working in industry or as practitioners (e.g. as teachers) for several years, and some even after they are about to or have already retired.

About 14,000 doctoral researchers have a Finnish nationality, 1,200 have an EU/EEA nationality, and about 3,400 have another nationality.

As the number of doctoral researchers has grown, however, so has also their unemployment. However, the unemployment rate of doctorate holders is still only around 4% (compared to 8% in the entire population) [46]. Currently, Finnish HE institutions are attempting to promote careers outside of academia for their doctoral graduates. The careers of PhD graduates are monitored by Aarressaari [47].

Looking at the staff (any) working in Finnish HE institutions, in 2021 there were about 42,000 people working in Finnish universities or universities of applied sciences (UAS): 18,400 men and 23,600 women. 35,000 had a Finnish nationality, and 7,000 had another nationality.

Looking at researchers, specifically, the number of people in different career stages was as follows:

CAREER STAGE	NUMBER OF PERSON/YEAR
Doctoral researcher	6.176 [48]
Postdoctoral researcher	4.817
University lecturer/professor	4.488
Professor	2.308
Teachers on hourly contracts	964

[44]<https://www.ksml.fi/paikalliset/2416477>

[45]<https://yle.fi/a/3-11050423>

[46]<https://sites.utu.fi/hiiskuttua/tohtorit-tyoelamassa-mita-vaittelyn-jalkeen/>

[47]<https://www.aarressaari.net/doctoral-degree-career-monitoring/?lang=en>

[48]Note that the number of doctoral researchers in this table is lower than the overall enrollment number presented earlier because not all doctoral researchers doing their doctorate in Finnish universities are employed by their university but instead are funded in other ways, such as external grants.

There is a great deal of research done on academic careers in the Finnish context. As Siekkinen and colleagues have summarised in their article [49], also Finnish universities follow global trends and have therefore become more market-oriented within the past years. When the new Universities Act came into effect in 2010, people working in universities were no longer working in a “public office” but instead had working contracts, and universities became economic entities with their own human resource management policies. In the following years, university mergers began taking place: Aalto University in 2010 and Tampere University in 2019). These mergers have affected the identities on an organisational, disciplinary, and individual level.

ACADEMIC SYSTEM IN THE COUNTRY

In 2022, there are 14 universities and 24 universities of applied sciences (UAS) in Finland. 13 universities operate under the Ministry of Education and culture, and one under the Ministry of Defense. 22 UAS operate under the Ministry of Education and Culture, one under the Ministry of the Interior, and one under the regional government of the Åland Islands. There are different legal bases for both: Universities can operate as corporations under public law, or as foundations, whereas UAS operate as public limited companies. Universities and UAS have different roles when it comes to education, research, and societal tasks. Whereas both can offer bachelor's and master's degrees, only universities grant doctoral degrees.

Although universities and UAS are typically perceived as different entities, UAS have increased their R&I activities, which has blurred the divide of the two sectors. However, the core funding is quite different: Universities get 42 percent of their core funding based on education outputs, 34 percent based on research outputs, and 24 percent based on strategic tasks and specific national duties, whereas UAS receive 76% of their core funding based on education outputs, 19% based on R&D, and 5% based on strategic tasks.

Population of students (2021)

312,834 (the Vipunen database)

Tertiary education attainment (2020)

44,7% (OECD; age group: 25-34)

Student-academic staff ratio in tertiary education (2018)

15,3 (Eurostat)

Public spending on tertiary education as % of GDP (2017)

1,6552% (World Bank)

Fees

See Eurydice Report 2020/2021 (p. 78) [50]

International students (% of total) (2018)

8,1% (OECD)

Main international student origin countries

Russia, Vietnam, China, Nepal, India (degree students; National Board of Education)

In addition to HEIs, there are the following Science Agencies, Research Institutes, and Scientific Organisations in Finland, as listed by the Ministry of Education and Culture [51]:

Science agencies and research institutes under the steering of the Ministry of Education and Culture

- [Academy of Finland](#)
- [The National Archives of Finland](#)
- [The Institute for the Languages of Finland](#)
- [The National Repository Library \(NRL\)](#)

State research institutes (State research institutes under the steering of other administrative sectors)

- [Geological Survey of Finland](#)
- [Finnish Meteorological Institute](#)
- [Natural Resources Institute Finland \(Luke\)](#)
- [The National Land Survey of Finland](#)
- [Finnish Food Authority](#)
- [Finnish Environment Institute](#)
- [Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority](#)
- [VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland](#)
- [The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare \(THL\)](#)
- [Finnish Institute of Occupational Health](#)
- [Finnish Institute of International Affairs](#)
- [VATT Institute for Economic Research](#)

Other expert bodies and collaborative organisations in science and research

- [Research and Innovation Council](#)
- [The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies](#)
- [Private Archives Association](#)
- [The Finnish Cultural and Academic Institutes](#)
- [The Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK](#)
- [The Committee for Public Information \(TJNK\)](#)
- [Tutkimuslaitosten yhteenliittymä Tulanet](#)
- [The Council of Finnish Academies](#)
- [The Finnish Society of Sciences and Letters](#)
- [Academia Scientiarum Fennica](#)
- [Finnish academy of technical sciences TTA](#)

CAREER TRACK FOR RESEARCHER IN THE COUNTRY

In Finland, there are a couple of different career progression models. The first is the 4-stage career model:

1. Doctoral researchers
2. Postdoctoral researchers
3. University lecturers/researchers
4. Professors

Levels 1 and 2 are characterised by temporary employment contracts, uncertainty, and less power, whereas levels 3 and 4 are characterised by permanent employment contracts, less uncertainty, and more power [52]. However, these stages do not represent a “pipeline” that a researcher can choose to take or apply to. Instead, career progression typically happens by applying for open positions on the next level. The higher the position, the fewer open positions there are. The tenure track system is becoming more and more common, though the criteria for tenure in different universities vary (see the dissertation by Pietilä [53]). As Siekkinen et al. [54] state, both models have been criticised, though they have offered some structure and clarity for academics’ career progression.

In 2021, the staff working in Finnish HEIs (incl. researchers, teachers, and administration) had the following types of contracts [55]:

TYPE OF CONTRACT	NUMBER OF PERSON/YEARS
Permanent, full-time	21.340
Permanent, part-time	1.255

[52] <https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/handle/10024/74897>

[53] <https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10138/234221>

[54] <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-019-00422-3>

[55] https://vipunen.fi/fi-fi/_layouts/15/xlviewer.aspx?id=/fi-fi/Raportit/Korkeakoulutus%20ja%20TK-toiminta%20-%20henkil%C3%B6st%C3%B6%20-%20henkil%C3%B6ty%C3%B6vuodet.xlsx

Permanent, full-time

21.340

Temporary, full-time

15.561

Temporary, part-time

2.741

Although there are a great deal of permanent, full-time contracts, they are usually not held by early-career researchers (doctoral or postdoctoral researchers), who mostly work on temporary employment contracts or external research grants, for example.

The Finnish Union of University Researchers and Teachers “are constantly negotiating with the employer on matters related to fixed-term employment contracts of members, such as turning the employment into permanent or paying compensation at the end of the employment if there were no legal grounds for the fixed-term employment.”, as there should always be a reason for making an employment contract temporary rather than permanent. The Union recommends “having the fixed-term employment relationship always cover the entire period of time required for the grounds for fixed-term employment [56](e.g. the entire period of deputyship). It is tactless towards the employee to only conclude fixed-term employment relationships lasting a couple of months with them while knowing that the project or deputyship in question will, in fact, last several years. Using very brief, fixed-term employment relationships often indicates poor work organisation skills, increases the stress of employees and weakens the university sector’s appeal as a workplace.”

Here, doctoral researchers are in a particularly difficult position, as their work usually has grounds for being temporary: the duration of the PhD. However, becoming a doctoral researcher in a Finnish university does not necessitate funding. Instead, one applies for a doctoral programme based on a research plan and becomes accepted (or not). However, gaining the study right in a specific programme does not automatically mean funding from the university, though some doctoral researcher positions are advertised as any university job. It is highly common, by contrast, that doctoral researcher does not have funding at the start of their studies. Instead, they begin their doctoral work alongside another job (in a university or elsewhere) and apply for grants and other similar funding later. Some might also be self-funded. In some cases, no funding is obtained and the doctoral researcher either quits their studies or completes the degree without ever being funded [57]. This, again, is problematic, as universities get funding from each publication, as well as for each graduate doctorate holder [58] .

Regarding doctoral education, each doctoral researcher belongs to a doctoral programme, no matter what their employment or funding status is. Each university and doctoral programme can organise doctoral studies as they wish, but the degree is planned in a way that it ought to be possible to finish in four years (with full-time work). The degree (240 credits in total) typically includes a doctoral thesis and 40 study credits of “other studies”, which are defined by the programme or the faculty. Overall, doing a PhD in Finland is highly independent work. Some researchers are part of research groups, some are not.

[56] <https://tieteentekijat.fi/en/support-of-working-life/fixed-term-employment/>

[57] <https://tieteentekijat.fi/uutishuone/liiton-julkaisut/>

[58] <https://okm.fi/-/korkeakoululle-uusi-rahoitusmalli>

Interestingly, a study by Pyhältö et al. [59] conducted in the Finnish context revealed that about one-third of all studied doctoral researchers did not feel they were part of any scholarly community, which affected both doctoral researchers' wellbeing and their commitment to their studies.

Recently, several Finnish universities have moved on to use the term "doctoral researcher" (väitöskirjatutkija) to refer to those doing their PhD [60, 61, 62]. This is in line with arguments made by Roitto and Impola [63], for example (see also other sources 64, 65, 66): Doing doctoral research differs significantly from bachelor's and master's level studies, as it is more independent. Doctoral researchers are often in employment relationships and producing publications and teaching like any other researcher. Moreover, the word "researcher" includes more agency than "student" or "trainee" does. Finally, being called "a student" might have negative consequences when applying for a mortgage at a bank, for example. While some research literature still uses the term "doctoral student", "doctoral researcher" is increasingly seen in studies on doctoral education, especially in the European context.

Researchers who have studied academic careers and academics in Finland (the list is not exhaustive):

- Melina Aarnikoivu (doctoral education, early-career researchers)
- Johanna Annala (teachers' work, academic communities)
- Anduena Ballo (doctoral researchers' wellbeing)
- David Hoffman (academic mobility patterns, international migration, knowledge society discourses)
- Jawaria Khan (brain-drain; internationalisation of Finnish HE)
- Jussi Kivistö (higher education institutions)
- Charles Mathies (internationalisation of HE)
- Terhi Nokkala (higher education policy, technological developments, individual experiences in higher education)
- Elias Pekkola (higher education institutions, leadership, academic work)
- Marja Peura (doctoral education)
- Maria Pietilä (tenure track)
- Kirsi Pyhältö (doctoral researcher)
- Taina Saarinen (higher education policy, internationalisation of higher education, languages in higher education, education policy, academic wellbeing)
- Taru Siekkinen (academic careers, hybridism)
- Jani Ursin (academic work, mergers)
- Jussi Välimaa (higher education systems, change in HE)
- Leasa Weimer (internationalisation of HE, transnational academic mobility)
- Oili-Helena Ylijoki (academic work and careers)
- Gaoming Zheng (doctoral education)

The biggest clusters of researchers specialising in higher education studies can be found at Tampere University (the groups HEG and HET) and the University of Jyväskylä (the group HIEST). Additionally, there are individual researchers or small groups of researchers working in different Finnish HEIs on a variety of topics related to academia and academics. Many of them are members of CHERIE, the Consortium of Higher Education Researchers in Finland.

[59] <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13601440903106551>

[60] <https://www.utu.fi/fi/ajankohtaista/uutinen/tohtorikoulutettavia-kutsutaan-jatkossa-vaitoskirjatutkijoiksi>

[61] <https://www.helsinki.fi/fi/uutiset/yliopisto/tohtorikoulutettavan-nimike-muuttuu-vaitoskirjatutkijaksi>

[62] <https://www oulu.fi/fi/uutiset/vaitoskirjatutkijan-nimike-kayttoon-oulu-yliopistossa>

[63] http://jargonja.fi/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/1_Jargonja_33_p%C3%A4%C3%A4kirjoitus_RoittoMatti_ImpolaPetteri.pdf

[64] <https://akatemiajulkavaki.fi/2022/04/22/vaitoskirjatutkija-on-enemman-tutkija-kuin-opiskelija/>

[65] https://arkisto.acatimi.fi/6_2017/14.php

[66] <https://jyx.jyu.fi/handle/123456789/71220>

CLIMATE AROUND MENTAL HEALTH AND WELL-BEING - IN GENERAL AND IN ACADEMIA

Although mental health and wellbeing get some attention in Finland (as illustrated in Section 1 of this report), mental health has not been widely discussed in Finnish academia. However, there is some change to be seen in this, as some Finnish universities have made wellbeing one of their top priorities [67, 68]. For example, the Rector of the University of Eastern Finland, Tapio Määttä, regularly tweets about different wellbeing initiatives of the university [69], emphasising the importance of wellbeing among students and also the staff.

There is also some research on mental health and wellbeing in academia, though a lot of it focuses on students. However, there are some ongoing studies on the topic, such as the AHJO project (Individual and organisational development of Academic wellbeing) [70]. Prior studies on the mental health and wellbeing of academic staff (mostly on doctoral researchers) include:

- Ala-Kauhaluoma, M., & Henriksson, M. (2011). Akateemisten pätkätöläisten hyvinvointi ja kuntoutus. TUULI-kehittämishankkeen arvioinnin loppuraportti. <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/27785>
- Harju, T. (2017). Kirjallisuuskatsaus yliopistojen työhyvinvointitutkimuksista (Master's thesis).
- Oksanen, A., Celuch, M., Latikka, R., Oksa, R., & Savela, N. (2022). Hate and harassment in academia: The rising concern of the online environment. *Higher Education*, 84(3), 541-567. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-021-00787-4>
- Pyhältö, K., Tikkanen, L., & Anttila, H. (2022). The influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on PhD candidates' study progress and study wellbeing. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2022.2063816>

[67] <https://www.jyu.fi/en/university/strategy-2030/community>

[68] <https://www.uef.fi/en/an-academic-community-characterised-by-well-being>

[69] <https://twitter.com/tapiomaatta/status/1372542394814586880>

[70] https://kti.jyu.fi/fi/henkilosto/saarinen-taina/ahjo_en

- Pyhältö, K., Toom, A., Stubb, J., & Lonka, K. (2012). Challenges of Becoming a Scholar: A Study of Doctoral Students' Problems and Well-Being. *ISRN Education, 2012*, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5402/2012/934941>
- Stubb, J., Pyhältö, K., & Lonka, K. (2011). Balancing between inspiration and exhaustion: PhD students' experienced socio-psychological well-being. *Studies in Continuing Education, 33*(1), 33-50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0158037X.2010.515572>
- Ylijoki, O-H. & Mäntylä, H. (2003).. Conflicting time perspectives in academic work *Time & Society, 12*(1), 55-78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961463X03012001364>

In the 2012 study by Pyhältö et al., it was reported that doctoral researchers reported a wide range of problems that occurred during their studies: general working processes, domain-specific expertise, supervision, the scholarly community, and resources. There was a clear relationship between doctoral researchers' wellbeing and study engagement. Ten years later, in 2022, another study by Pyhältö and colleagues was published, which showed that the pandemic had slowed down their PhD progress and decreased their study wellbeing, especially for international doctoral researchers.

In addition to the above research, in 2020 and 2021 the Finnish Union for University Researchers and Teachers sent a survey to its members, asking about wellbeing during the pandemic [71]. The 2021 results (n=1124) showed, among other things, that:

- 29% of those working in research-oriented positions, 73% of those working in teaching oriented-positions, and 65% of those working in administrative-oriented positions had an increased workload compared to pre-pandemic times
- 13% of all respondents felt that their work had gone badly or very badly during the pandemic
- 42% of all respondents felt that their work-related wellbeing has decreased during the pandemic
- The most challenging aspects of working during the pandemic were: less social contacts (58% of all respondents); work ergonomics when working at a distance (47%); blurred work and free time (47%); the increased pace of work due to meetings following one another, for example (28%)
- 38% of all respondents reported that they would've needed more support from their direct supervisor during the pandemic
- 9% of all respondents felt that their employer had done poorly or very poorly during the pandemic

In a forthcoming European-wide report on the pandemic and higher education [72], results from eight different countries, including Finland [73], will be reported. The results will highlight differences between different countries in terms of how well different HE systems and academics coped with COVID-19. The report will be published in early 2023.

[71] <https://tieteentekijat.fi/tieteentekijan-arki/tyohyvinyvointi/>

[72] <https://projects.au.dk/european-universities-critical-futures/pandemic-study>

[73] The Finnish research team consisted of Taina Saarinen and Melina Aarnikoivu.

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MENTAL HEALTH SUPPORT AND SERVICE SYSTEMS

As described by Mieli, in Finland “municipal authorities are responsible for organising mental health services. Mental health services are also provided by hospital districts, private service providers and third sector actors, i.e. different kinds of organisations” [74]. For example, one of the private health care providers, Terveystalo, which offers occupational health care services for Finnish universities, has services related to “wellbeing at work” (“työssäjaksaminen”) [75].

Some universities have offered mental health first aid training sessions for students and staff [76]. Such materials and tailored training sessions are offered by Mieli - Mental Health Finland [77]. Sadly, even though services exist, the Finnish media often reports on long queues to access mental health services [78, 79, 80, 81] although usually they apply to young people in particular.

[74] <https://mieli.fi/en/mental-ill-health/how-to-seek-help/mental-health-services/>

[75] <https://www.terveystalo.com/fi/palvelut/tyossa-jaksaminen>

[76] <https://www.aalto.fi/fi/palvelut/mielenterveyden-ensiapukurssit-r-aaitolaisille>

[77] <https://mieli.fi/materiaalit-ja-koulutukset/>

[78] <https://www.vantaansanomat.fi/paikalliset/4454588>

[79] <https://yle.fi/a/3-12183707>

[80] <https://yle.fi/a/3-12265540>

[81] <https://www.medi uutiset.fi/uutiset/keusotessa-loydettiin-keino-purkaa-mielenterveyspalvelujen-jonot-sita-on-pyrittty-lisaamaan-vaikuttavien-tulosten-vuoksi/00cca72d-3ce9-44c1-97a5-565300020fb1>

WORKPLACE OF ACADEMIA, EMPLOYMENT

As a workplace, academia does not significantly differ from other workplaces where knowledge work is being done. And, even though Finnish academia is not immune to issues such as overworking, burnouts, harassment, bullying, or similar, the Finnish working culture is generally somewhat healthy. For instance, it is ok to say that one is on holiday, to take full holidays, and to not work during the weekends. Most people arrive in the office around 8 or 9, and leave between 16 and 17. Working from home is usually fine, and many have decided to continue “flexiwork” even after the pandemic restrictions have ended. This makes sense, as distances between cities and towns in Finland are quite long, and many live far away from campus.

Universities are regulated by the University Act [82], which includes 11 sections, including the ones on Research and Teaching (Section 2) and Staff and administrative language (Section 4). The General Collective Agreement for universities specifies that the annual working time of (full-time) university teaching and research staff is 1,612 hours. Each employee is responsible for planning their own working time and using it according to their work plan. Work plans are monitored by the employee (usually by the direct supervisor). The work plan includes research, teaching, administrative, or other duties, depending on the position. It also includes extended absences, such as family leaves.

Once fulfilling the requirement of 1,612 hours, research and teaching staff can have **holidays** whenever they see fit. Usually, this amounts to about 6 weeks of holidays per year. Generally, most people take 1-2 weeks during Christmas time, and 4-5 weeks during the summer, usually in July. Given that the Finnish schools often start their summer holidays in the first days of June and return to school in the 2nd week of August, most academics who are parents have their holidays within that period.

[82]<https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/2009/20090558>

Family **leave** follows the same regulations as in other Finnish workplaces [83].

It consists of:

- **pregnancy leave** and special pregnancy leave, which lasts for 40 working days and usually begins 30 days before the due date. Pregnancy leave must be started at least 14 weekdays before the due date;
- **parental leave**, to which both parents are entitled. Only one parent at a time can be on parental leave, except for 18 working days, which can be shared. The parental leave lasts for 320 working days (about 14 months). Both parents are therefore entitled to 160 working days' leave. A maximum of 63 parental leave days can be given to the other parent. Parental leave can also be part-time;
- **child care leave**, which means that a parent can stay on leave until the child turns 3.

The parental allowance during these leaves depends on the leave and the person's current employment and salary.

The Finnish social security is available to those who live in the country permanently [84]. To be entitled to earnings-related unemployment benefits, one usually has to be part of a Finnish unemployment fund. For example, the Finnish Union of University Researchers and Teachers has such a fund, and to be a member of the Union, one has to pay 1% of one's salary (gross) as a membership fee [85]. More information on working time, annual leave, and payments are specified by the Finnish Union for University Researchers and Teachers [86].

As specified on the University of Jyväskylä website [87] "[t]he statutory pension security in Finland consists of earnings-related pension based on employment and residence-based national pension. Most people in Finland only receive the earnings-related pension. [...] Earnings-related pensions are compulsory and they are arranged by the employer. Earnings-related pensions are paid for by both the employer and the employee and the employee part of the pension payment is deducted automatically from the employee's salary. [...] In addition to the employee pension payment, an unemployment insurance payment amounting to 1,4% will be deducted from your salary."

Doctoral researchers who work in Finnish universities on an external or internal grant (so not in an employment relationship) for more than 4 months, must apply for insurance from Mela, (the Farmers' Social Insurance Institution) [88] instead. This means that they pay a small sum from their grant to gain insurance. In this way, grant researchers are in a more equal position when it comes to pensions, for example. However, the weaker status of grant researchers has been criticised [89, 90, 91], as they are not entitled to workplace healthcare like the ones in an employment relationship are. In some universities, they also do not get an office (or they have to pay for one), or even an access card. This, in turn, might lead to a lack of peer support and other important communities that are needed on doctoral journeys. Luckily, some universities have actively worked on improving the status of grant researchers [92, 93], by offering them a small part-time employment contract, for example.

[83] <https://www.infofinland.fi/en/work-and-enterprise/employees-rights-and-obligations/family-leave>

[84] <https://www.infofinland.fi/settling-in-finland/finnish-social-security>

[85] <https://tieteentekijat.fi/en/membership/membership-fees/>

[86] <https://tieteentekijat.fi/en/support-of-working-life/working-time-and-absences/>

[87] <https://www.jyu.fi/en/workwithus/international-staff-guide/living-in-finland/pension>

[88] <https://www.mela.fi/en/grant-and-scholarship-recipients/>

[89] <https://www.hs.fi/mielipide/art-2000004863411.html>

[90] <https://tieteentekijat.fi/mita-apurahatutkijoille-kuuluu-raportti-julkaistu/>

[91] <https://ylioppilaslehti.fi/2021/05/apurahatutkijan-tyoolot-ovat-yliopistoissa-yleensa-huomattavasti-huonommat-kuin-tyosuhteen-tutkijan-yliopistoille-he-ovat-kuitenkin-monin-tavoin-arvokkaita/>

[92] <https://www.helsinki.fi/fi/uutiset/korkeakoulupolitiikka/apurahatutkijan-asema-paranee-helsingin-yliopistossa>

[93] <https://www.uef.fi/fi/artikkeli/ita-suomen-yliopisto-parantaa-apurahatutkijoidensa-asemaa-tarjolla-osa-aikainen-tyosuuhde>

POLICY VIEW ON MENTAL HEALTH/ WELL-BEING

The legislation in Finland includes the following:

- Mental Health Act [94]
- Employment Contract Act [95]
- Working Time Act [96]
- Occupational Health Care Act [97]
- Non-discrimination Act [98]

In the final one, it says (loosely translated): “No one is allowed to be discriminated based on their age, origin, nationality, language, religion, beliefs, opinions, political activity, trade union activity, family ties, health status, disability, sexual orientation, or other person-related issues.”

Additionally, there is a Non-Discrimination Ombudsman in Finland [99], who is also involved in suspected discrimination cases in Finnish universities [100].

Typically, Finnish HEIs have extensive well-being and “sports services” for their staff. For example, at the University of Jyväskylä, staff members can spend 2 hours per week (of their work time) on sporting activities. Additionally, the university offers a great deal of courses related to wellbeing and sports for their staff [101]. Sometimes, these courses are organised for both students and staff.

[94] <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/1990/1990116>

[95] <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/2001/20010055>

[96] <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/2019/20190872>

[97] <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/2001/20011383>

[98] <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/alkup/2014/20141325>

[99] <https://syrjinta.fi/en/front-page>

[100] <https://yle.fi/a/3-12180797>

[101] <https://www.jyu.fi/fi/yliopisto/tyopaikat/henkilostoedut-hyvinvointi>

STAKEHOLDERS AND POLICIES

The largest advocate for mental health in Finland is the Mieli Association [102]. Their website is now in Finnish, Swedish, English, Arabic, Russian, and Ukrainian.

There are different associations, trade unions, and interest groups related to Finnish higher education. Occasionally, these groups give out statements about researchers' wellbeing, too:

- Universities Finland (UNIFI) [103]. In a statement made in 2020, UNIFI committed to working on equity and safety in Finnish academia [104].
- The Finnish Union of University Researchers and Teachers [105]
- The Finnish Union of University Professors [106]
- The Rectors' Conference of Finnish Universities of Applied Sciences Arene [107]
- Edistysellinen tiedeliitto (Progressive research association) [108]
- Many disciplines and fields also have their own, discipline-specific networks or associations that publish academic journals or organise events for their members

Traditionally, trade unions have had a strong role in the Finnish society. Around 60-70% of all Finnish employees are members of a trade union. Women are members slightly more often than men. Especially in industry jobs, it is common to be a union member [109]. Akava, which is the central union of 36 affiliates for highly educated professionals, has about 600,000 members [110].

During the mental health awareness week, there are several events around the country, also in universities [111, 112, 113, 114]

[102]<https://mieli.fi/en/>

[103]<https://unifi.fi/en/>

[104]<https://unifi.fi/uutiset/hairinta-ja-syrjinta-eivat-kuulu-yliopistoyhteisoon/>

[105]<https://tieteentekijat.fi/en/home/>

[106]<https://www.professoriliitto.fi/in-english/>

[107]<https://www.arene.fi/the-rectors-conference-of-finnish-universities-of-applied-sciences-arene/>

[108]<https://www.tiedeliitto.net/>

[109]<https://duunitori.fi/tyoelama/ammattiliitot>

[110]<https://akava.fi/en/affiliates/>

[111]<https://www.mtk.fi/toimintamme/tapahtumat-kurssit-koulutukset/mielenterveysviikko/>

[112]<https://studies.helsinki.fi/ohjeet/uutiset/mielenterveysviikko-muistuttaa-toivosta-ja-vertaistuesta-osallistu-yliopistolla-ja-etana>

[113]<https://yy.fi/tapahtuma/mielenterveysviikko-mental-health-week/>

[114]<https://sites.utu.fi/mielenpaalla/mielenterveysviikko-4-8-10/>

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EURAXESS CENTERS AS HUBS FOR SUPPORTING RESEARCHERS' MOBILITY AND CAREER

- All Finnish Euraxess centres (13 in total) are listed here: https://www.euraxess.fi/information/centres/search/country/finland-1071/field_category/3
- Eleven institutions in Finland have received the HR Excellence in Research award [115]
- Sixteen institutions in Finland have endorsed the Charter & Code principles [116]
- There is a Research and Innovation council (TIN) in Finland, led by the prime minister [117].

[115] <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/hrs4r/awarded>

[116] https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter/declaration-endorsement#show_Finland

[117] <https://valtioneuvosto.fi/tin>

EQUITY, DIVERSITY, INCLUSION, ACCESSIBILITY IN ACADEMIA

Universities have webpages, strategies, and working groups related to equity and diversity (and sometimes sustainability). Usually the web pages are in Finnish and English, sometimes also in Swedish:

- [Aalto University](#)
- [Hanken](#)
- [Tampere University](#)
- [University of Arts Helsinki](#)
- [University of Eastern Finland](#)
- [University of Turku](#)
- [University of Oulu](#)
- [University of Vaasa](#)
- [University of Lapland](#)
- [University of Jyväskylä](#)
- [University of Helsinki](#)
- [Åbo Akademi](#)

In Finland, Åbo Akademi led an Erasmus+ project called Projektet Designing and supporting inclusive practices in Higher Education (InclusiveHE) [118] which included partner universities from different European countries. Although this project was framed around students, many issues also concerned university staff. The project, for example, mapped out what kinds of documents there are on inclusivity in Finnish higher education. Such documents include:

- [The "OHO" guide](#), which focuses on improving student wellbeing. The guide, however, is in Finnish only.
- [Flexible Learning Pathways in Finnish Higher Education](#)
- [Individual study arrangements at Aalto University](#)
- [Celia - a library of accessible literature in Finland](#)
- [Background matters. Students with an immigrant background in higher education.](#)
- [Equality and non-discrimination plan](#)
- [Nordic Rebels: A Blended Approach to Fix Higher Education](#)

As Siekkinen et al. [119] have described, the level of internationalization in Finland has been somewhat low compared with other countries. International students (and staff are considered as highly-skilled labour and as a means to achieve global competitiveness. Research has shown, however, that international students and staff face challenges in Finnish society, for example, related to language skills (not knowing Finnish “well enough”).

As pointed out in Section 1 (News), in November 2022, a report commissioned by the Ministry of Education and Culture showed that Finnish higher education institutions still have much work to do in promoting equality for teaching and research staff [120, 121]. For example, it was found that ethnic minorities face discrimination almost twice as often as ethnic Finns. Moreover, research groups led by women were better balanced in terms of gender compared to the research groups led by men in all research fields. Women also witness discrimination in HEIs more than men. Statistically, gender inequality is best seen in the fact that there are significantly fewer women in the highest positions of an academic career, even though there are more women studying in universities.

[119]<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-019-00422-3>

[120]https://okm.fi/-/selvitys-korkeakoulujen-kiinnitettava-huomiota-etnisiin-vahemmistoihin-kuuluvan-henkiloston-tasa-arvoon?languageId=en_US (in English)
and https://okm.fi/-/selvitys-korkeakoulujen-kiinnitettava-huomiota-etnisiin-vahemmistoihin-kuuluvan-henkiloston-tasa-arvoon?languageId=fi_FI (in Finnish)

[121]<https://okm.fi/julkaisu?pubid=URN:ISBN:978-952-263-765-9>